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FLIPPING ALL COURSES ON A SEMESTER: STUDENTS REACTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Several universities have adopted flipped learning methods for teaching, offering increased student interaction, and different approaches to course preparation and learning processes. Flipped learning appears particularly well suited for engineering educations, as it can combine active and problem-based learning (PBL) activities. In spring 2019, a research project challenged a 4th semester at the Medialogy BSc programme to a 'flipped and integrated semester', where all courses applied flipped learning, and used the approach to integrate students' coursework into their semester project work. To measure the effect of the flipped and integrated semester approach, the 4th semester teacher team collaborated to include several initiatives, such as cross-course teaching activities, student activities for course- and project-integration, and integration-supporting supervision approaches, etc. Student responses to these changes were diverse, and while a part of the students were positive, there is a definite room for improvement. Most requested improvements included a strong semester structure and planning and an explicitly clear relationship between courses and the project. Flipped and integrated semesters require a lot of planning, communication, need a holistic structure and has to be transparently communicated to students. Also among students' main requests for improvement, were a consistent flipping approach across courses, clear connections between homework preparation material and in-class activities, and the inclusion of short introductory in-class clarification of preparation material before any in-class activities. If properly motivated to follow the steps, students found that the flipped classroom format could increase learning.

1 INTRODUCTION

Flipped learning approaches has been adapted by more and more universities, due to their ability to facilitate opportunities for expanded student interaction, and enhance the width of ways to engage the subject material. Having these freedoms can prove important for students' learning processes, if applied correctly (Johnson et al. 2015). From the combined perspectives of a constructivist ideology and instructional lectures, flipped learning approaches can be integrated advantageously within engineering educations, due to their handy consolidation of active and problem-based learning (PBL) activities (Karabulut-Ilgü et al. 2018). A variety of studies have been published on applying flipped classroom, flipped learning and blended learning to lectures. Between these studies, very different experiences has been reported between students and teachers, for instance in terms best practice on structure, learning outcome and resources needed to fulfill the requirements (Triantafyllou et al. 2016; Bertel & Svarre Kristensen 2018).

Since 1976, Aalborg University has applied its *AAU Model*, which includes the *AAU PBL principles* (Askehave et al. 2015) to guide teaching praxis: project organization creates the framework of PBL; courses support the project work; cooperation is a driving force in problem-based project work; the problem-based project work of the groups must be exemplary; students are responsible for their own learning achievements (Askehave et al. 2015). The principles cover three learning dimensions: 1) the problem, 2) the content and 3) the team. The typical application of the AAU PBL principles, if regarded from the perspective of semester construction, includes a governing semester description (the semester theme) to frame the scope, a set of courses which students follow for basic knowledge, skills and competences, and a problem-based semester project with learning objectives congruent with the semester theme.

The AAU Model has occasionally been revised to remain contemporary. However, the 2011 revision introduced an alteration that challenged the inherent compass of AAU PBL (Hüttel & Gnaur 2017). All courses were now required to be individually examined, replacing a modus where a portion of courses were evaluated based on a) their integration in the semester project and b) the students' proficiencies with the course curriculum at the project examination. The adjustment to step away from the project as the governing body for a collective of learning objectives, can now be seen as deceptively impactful. The ensuing years has shown a slow but certain disunion of courses and projects. Their role as mutual partners, and 'keepers' of a forgathered semester theme, is now showing signs of discontinuance with both students and teachers.

A recent ambition for AAU has become to constructively challenge the comprehension of its 'AAU Model' PBL ideology. Examples showing this incentive are the close to 30 small, AAU-funded PBL projects, aimed for internal researchers to exploring, question, challenge or examine a slice of the AAU PBL praxis. Several of these concerned flipped classroom-oriented approaches. Additionally, AAU also funded the '*Future Directions for Problem Based Learning in a Digital Age*' project - or *PBL Future* for short (Pblfuture.aau.dk); a 3-year research project aimed for deeper understanding of the inner pros and cons workings of the current model implementation, as well as new visions to take the AAU PBL principles into the next revised era.

A 'PBL Future' sub-project research group (the authors of this paper) have specifically invested their research in exploring the utilization of flipped learning, as a standard teaching approach for the digitalized future of AAU PBL. In spring 2019, a concept termed '*a flipped and integrated semester*' was proposed by the research group to a

4th semester AAU teacher team, at the Medialogy B.Sc. program. In such 'flipped and integrated semester', all courses would solely practice a flipped learning approach in teaching, while also seeking integration of integrate (Kofoed et al. 2018).

Medialogy as a field combines problem-solving, human-computer interaction, design and media technology, to create specific solutions for specific users, often in collaboration with stakeholders. The 4th semester of Medialogy (MED4) at Aalborg University Copenhagen, consists of three courses (5 ECTS each) and a semester project (15 ECTS), and the semester theme is '*Sound Computing and Sensor Technology*'. MED4 relies more heavily on math and programming compared to previous semesters, focusing more towards understanding user needs. Empirical survey data suggests that this semester profile means that many Medialogy students consider MED4 a particularly difficult semester. This is supported by internal data showing that many students fail the ordinary MED4 course exams (Kofoed et al. 2018), suggesting an inadequate learning outcome. For years, this trend has frustrated the MED4 teacher team, and made them susceptible to alternative approaches.

The concept of a flipped and integrated semester within a PBL environment is pedagogically a fitting combination, from the theoretical perspective of Jensen et al. (2015). Both are rooted in active learning, and active participation has shown to lead to improved learning (Jensen et al. 2015), compared to passive learning which conversely has shown to impact performance negatively (Hackmann & Holmboe 2014). As one of the pioneers, Lage et al. (2000), defined a flipped (inverted) classroom as "*Inverting the classroom means that events that have traditionally taken place inside the classroom now are taking place outside the classroom and vice versa*" (Lage et al. 2000). Meanwhile, the 'flipped classroom' and 'flipped learning' concepts should not be confused as identical. Flipped classroom involves structure and framework of teaching, while flipped learning focuses on the processes and learning. The traditional, transmissive lecture is discharged with the flipped learning approach, overtaken by active in-class activities, for example peer learning, problem solving, and specific pedagogical approaches for out of class activities (Hackmann & Holmboe 2014). PBL is likewise occupied with active learning, as well as the emphasis on activating students in real-world oriented problem-solving processes, including peer learning.

The flipped and integrated semester was presented to the MED4 team including the following benefits: a) the support of a wider range of possible PBL-oriented student activities during in-class sessions, including even more student-teacher interaction, b) to increase connectedness between courses by (for instance) allowing more cross-and combined course dissemination and activities, and c) to introduce stronger integration of project and courses, by basing course activities on project-related needs, preparing initiating project descriptions which carefully subscribed to course contents, and to plan the sequencing of the courses to follow the project phases.

This paper marks the end of the first completion of such flipped and integrated semester; a 5-month process working with teachers to adapt flipped learning, as a tool to advance their teaching experiences, and invite them to test and explore the utilization of digitalized content distribution with new roles for the effective course dissemination. But more fundamentally; to reintroduce the explicit ambition of a cross-course and course-project integration to the AAU semester. This paper will primarily contribute to the PBL community, with a discussion of the flipped and integrated semester concept, largely based on a presentation of results from the concluding student evaluation of the first full iteration of the flipped and integrated semester.

2 METHODS

The three flipped semester courses were *Audio Processing (AP)*, *Design & Analysis of Experiments (DAE)*, and *Physical Interface Design (PID)*. DAE had experimented with flipped classroom prior to the flipped and integrated semester, but AP and PID had no experience. Leading up to semester start, teachers and PBL researchers discussed approaches to flipping, decided to approximate teachers' approach closely to DAE's adaptation; video material, readings and quizzes were provided for out-of-class homework preparation for the in-class session. In-class sessions started with a short discussion on the preparation homework, proceeding quickly to an activity-based scheme, typically group exercises performed with teacher/TA assistance, and routinely broken a bit, by the teacher calling for a short detailing to the whole class, if a challenge would telegraph itself likely to be shared by many students. AP and PID needed to find their feet in this approach, and find or develop out-of-class material. In addition, workshops were provided throughout the semester, providing an extended version of the in-class lecture activity scheme. Some workshops focused primarily on individual courses, while others sought to combine considerations both several courses and the semester project.

During the semester progression, the teacher team exchanged experiences internally and at meetings, and adjusted the teaching accordingly. Examples include the amount of readings, the explanation of the purpose of readings or tasks, the in-class sessions, etc. During the semester, one role of the PBL research team was to facilitate and (if needed) mediate the dialogues between teachers. Another was to observe and collect information and insights about the progress of the semester, based partly on observations, but also student responses from surveys regularly provided to students throughout the semester. The information from surveys was then presented to teachers, for them to adapt accordingly, if needed. The methodology for the research group was primarily approaching the study as an explorative case study (Stebbins 2001, Remenyi 2013), and a descriptive, mixed-method study (Stake 1995, Yin 2008). Four questionnaires were sent to students during the semester, focusing primarily on the same aspects. It is the fourth and final questionnaire, requesting students' final evaluation of the semester, which this paper focuses on. All the four questionnaires were built using predominantly quantitative rating on students' experience of the flipped lectures (as this would be the first time many of them had tried that). More specifically, main categories were the level of integration of project considerations in courses, students' perceived course workload, their perceived difficulty of the courses, and the perceived learning outcome from courses. Lastly, students were asked about the integration of course work into their project, and overall aspects to their semester project experience. The questionnaire had 44 quantitative items and 17 open-ended (qualitative) items, split into 15 small sections, covering the categories just mentioned. After each of the 15 sections, one of the 17 open-ended items would follow, as voluntary response options requesting elaboration from students on the ratings they gave in the section, if students would care to elaborate on their rating. Besides these follow-ups, the last open ended items were an opening "describe your MED4 experience" and a closing "if you have any additional comments, please add". In the following, we will present the evaluation results. The questionnaire was provided to students on October 8th 2019. At this time, all participating students had completed MED4, including all exams, and had a complete impression of the semester.

3 RESULTS

The questionnaire received 40 responses out of 59 registered students on the semester. This is considered a satisfactory cut of the population. The following results presentation will be disseminated in formulated form, with tendencies informed by the quantitative ratings, and rationalized based on the open-ended responses.

The key contribution here, is the summative conclusions and future recommendations to a flipped and integrating semester, from students who a) have been used to traditional course work + a weakly integrated PBL project, but b) is then removed completely from this comfort zone, c) exclusively exposed to flipped learning course-work for an entire semester, d) from teachers with mixed experiences, e) on a semester with a very steep learning curve, and f) with a semester coordinator who has had to understand how to plan the semester around it. Exposing the governing take-away already here; findings will suggest a definite potential for the flipped and integrated semester, but also show that flipped learning is a craft that needs a lot of initiating investments, practical experiences and specific application to the target audience. Another key finding is that flipping an entire semester at once, for the first time, is a deceptively large task, that demands constant and very high levels of communication between teachers, as well as frequent dialogue with students to understand their perceptions and needs.

In the opening item; the exclusively open-ended experience description from students, the semester was depicted with positive references from an overall appreciation of the holistic approach to the flipped courses, including the teaching method applied by teachers and coordinators for both for courses and workshops, and showed an appreciation of capable and engaged teachers. Critique was more dominant than praise, however, pointing towards an absence of consistency and structure in the implementation of the flipped learning approach, especially for the two courses where teachers had less experience. Arguments included an overly tight and stressed schedule, and an extensive out-of-class preparation quantities, which resulted in several topics covered in courses to manifest as a stressful experience. Another overall criticism was a perceived lack of coherence between the course curriculum as experienced during the lecture-run, compared to the final exam requirements.

For a more detailed look into some of these criticisms, responses on courses' *provided homework preparation material* prior to in-class activities was again perceived as well chosen by some students, while others criticised content. Argued by some to simply be 'boring', others raised quite relevant critiques by questioning the balance between the large preparation quantities and a perceived lack of useful application or logical purpose of the material, in relation to either the course learning objectives, or the transfer of the material into the in-class sessions. Students suggested a priority system (e.g. a split between mandatory and extended readings). Other critiques related to preparation material not produced by the teachers themselves, which made it feel distant, inadequate or irrelevant to the following in-class activity.

Concerning the *in-class activities* themselves, some students considered them fruitful and constructive for the understanding of the overall lecture content, though with a differentiating rank between the individual courses. Endorsements related to proper balancing and logic between preparation and in-class activities, but only if in-class sessions included good introductions to the prepared material, and was complemented with clear descriptions of the expected application and outcomes for the in-class exercises. Appreciation was also given to sessions including considerations or practical work supporting the semester project. Critique aimed at in-

class sessions that served as mere repetition of the homework preparation, and when the connection from preparation material to in-class activities became too abstract to transfer. Or if activities were simply too difficult compared to the preparation material. Regarding *difficulty*, positive responses pointed towards the importance of a clear structure, clear relations between homework and in-class teaching, and the overall description of the course vision. Consistency on these aspects lowered the risk of misinterpreting the actual difficulty level. Interestingly, students reported that a lack of structure made them estimate the course difficulty as either very easy or very difficult. But generally, if the transfer of preparation material content into in-class sessions appeared abstract or unclear, students typically perceived lectures to be very difficult. During such in-class sessions, students reported to request more step-by-step explanations and practical examples of homework application. High course difficulty was also related to lacking structure, especially when an exam assignment did not reflect the learning objectives that students experienced from either preparation material or in-class exercise sessions. Only the already flipped-experienced DAE course, was mentioned to appear balanced.

Students' *perceived learning outcome* was rated with a high learning outcome for coursework with clear structure, in-class processes that were well planned with clear goals, and which included the before-mentioned 'initiating coverage' of the homework preparation material in the opening phases of the in-class session, ensuring the perspective for students. When not in place, ratings were noticeably lower, which also including prior mentioned issues, such as when material or in-class sessions were too abstract, too high-level, without a clear purpose, or disconnected homework and in-class tasks. Interestingly, quite a few student responses included self-reports on moments where their learning outcome had suddenly increased dramatically, and that they did this at very different phases in the semester/course in question *and* through very different activities, with some students reporting that their epiphany occurred during a home-preparation session, while had it at an in-class activity, and some even only during the exam preparations.

Looking at the *integration of courses into the project*, the DAE course was the only course consistently represented in the project. When looking at ratings on the *overall project experience*, they suggest that while students found between-students groupwork quite satisfactory, this was less so with supervision and exams. Comments suggest that expectations may not have been sufficiently aligned, in terms of what the students expected the project / supervisor to need or result with. Prominent complaints from students in this regard focuses on the exam, and how supervisors were focusing a lot on the application of knowledge from the courses, in the project.

The last open-ended item; *students final recommendations*, focused in part on the *overall semester and course structure*, requesting clear and explicit relationships between courses and semester project. *Cross-course workshops* was highlighted as very useful for the integration of courses and project work. In relation to *semester planning and preparation*, the semester should be a well-planned, clearly structured 'whole'. This includes clear and transparent progressions through the courses, an overview of the entire semester, and better communication across courses, especially on assignments and increased workload phases, in order to avoid overlap. Students stated the need of developing a *consistent and logical flipped learning approach*, where all courses on the semester should apply a coherently similar approach. A clear *connection between homework preparation material and in-class activities* creates motivation to prepare, which can make the flipped classroom format work very well, and in fact increases learning. During in-class sessions, students besides valuing the

introductory in-class clarification, students also recommended using smaller, quicker assignments, possibly then in higher numbers, so tasks can be finished within the in-class session and utilize the format.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

There are some very central, interesting and useful tendencies in the data. While the students who expressed complete positivity with the whole flipped and integrated semester-initiative were in fact an overall minority, the issues brought up by the latter students are both logical and approachable for improvement. It also shows that implementing flipped learning is not simply about time-switching, but a craft in itself, that also very proficient teachers need to get familiar with over time. The issues with the flipped teaching approach, leaves the question of whether flipped learning is constructive for integration difficult to answer clearly. Integration suffered an underwhelmingly representation in the student responses, due to other matters that related to start-up difficulties for some teachers, in some phases of the semester. It therefore remains to be seen how well flipped learning can indeed become a catalyst for increased integration. Student responses were, however, always positive about course/project integration, both when it happened, and being discontent when it should have. Returning to the flipped learning, it appears that suboptimal application of flipped learning can have radiant consequences on students' perceptions of learning outcome and difficulty. This returns the focus to how flipped learning, with all its moving parts and possibly heavier self-study loads and requirements. It appears to be able to develop specific pressure points, where the approach *has* to deliver, to avoid students losing overview, perceiving the workload to increase, or lose their orientation of purpose or transfer of e.g. material into a meaningful application in another phase of the flipped cycle.

If anything, it could appear that flipped learning *needs* to have its methodological and pedagogical sweet spot established, to allow meaningful integration between courses and into the projects. Naturally, much of students' criticism was built on imbalances with semester coordination, course structures, flipped approach coherency, workload planning and met expectations.

It however is very interesting to see, how students independently reported when they suddenly hit a spot where their learning outcome was increased dramatically, because they finally understood the bigger picture. Observing the AP course, it consistently improved these aspects; structure, planning, in-class introductions, workload regulations, preparation material adaptation, etc. The course was gradually optimized during the semester, as the teachers became aware of the issues and solutions recommended by students, and certain students' feedback on when they started learning much more fits the timeline well.

Overall, there are still too much potential, and too concretely improvable solutions, to dismiss the idea of the flipped and integrated semester. Future iterations are bound to be facilitated, based on the experiences obtained in this initiating iteration. It is interesting, that students are suddenly requesting structure, vision, planning, coherency, etc., when faced with the flipped learning. One reflection of that relates exactly to the integration perspective. Future research will hopefully provide more concrete answer, but if one imagines that students actually started to care about the transfer, logic, academic and theme-oriented connectedness, because they now saw that it was theoretically possible; that is a nice motivator to continue the work.

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